

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Hand Hygiene Compliance Strategies across Different Departments in a Tertiary Hospital

Eyan M. Alsomali¹, Suliman Almojaly², Ali S. Aldossari³,
Mariam W. Alanazi⁴

Health Affairs at the Ministry of National Guard

Abstract

Hand hygiene is a critical component of infection control in healthcare settings, yet compliance among healthcare workers varies significantly across departments. This study evaluated hand hygiene compliance rates in a tertiary hospital, focusing on emergency, radiology, and intensive care units, using a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative findings revealed that compliance was highest in the ICU (78%) and lowest in radiology (52%). Thematic analysis of qualitative data identified workload, leadership support, and resource availability as key factors influencing compliance. These findings suggest that tailored, department-specific interventions, including leadership engagement and infrastructural improvements, are necessary to improve hand hygiene practices.

Keywords: Hand Hygiene, Infection Control, Compliance, Healthcare Workers, Tertiary Hospital, Mixed-Methods, Leadership, Resource Availability

Introduction

Effective hand hygiene is a fundamental component of infection control in healthcare settings, significantly reducing the transmission of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) (WHO, 2009). Despite its importance, ensuring compliance with hand hygiene guidelines remains a challenge, even in tertiary hospitals with access to the necessary resources (Allegranzi&Pittet, 2009). Compliance rates among healthcare workers can vary substantially across different hospital departments due to a range of factors, such as workload, departmental culture, and the physical environment (Erasmus et al., 2009).

The World Health Organization (WHO) and other health authorities have developed various strategies to improve hand hygiene compliance, including educational campaigns, reminders, and performance feedback (WHO, 2009). However, the effectiveness of these interventions can differ based on the context in which they are implemented. For instance, departments with high patient turnover, such as emergency or radiology, may face more barriers to compliance compared to other settings (Pittet, 2001). Understanding these differences is critical to tailoring interventions that address the specific challenges faced by different departments.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of hand hygiene compliance strategies across various departments in a tertiary hospital. By examining compliance rates and identifying department-specific barriers and facilitators, this research seeks to contribute to the development of targeted interventions that can enhance hand hygiene practices, ultimately reducing the risk of HAIs and improving patient safety.

Literature Review

Hand hygiene is widely recognized as one of the most effective measures for reducing the transmission of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs). According to the World Health Organization (2009), adherence to hand hygiene practices has been shown to significantly reduce the risk of cross-infection in healthcare settings. However, compliance with hand hygiene guidelines remains a persistent challenge, particularly in high-pressure environments such as tertiary hospitals. Studies have identified a range of factors contributing to poor compliance, including heavy workload, inadequate staffing, time constraints, and lack of access to necessary resources (Erasmus et al., 2009).

Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) highlighted that the success of hand hygiene interventions is often influenced by the culture within healthcare institutions. Institutional culture plays a critical role in shaping attitudes and behaviors towards infection control practices. For example, healthcare workers in departments with strong leadership support and a positive safety culture are more likely to comply with hand hygiene guidelines. Conversely, departments with insufficient support and high levels of stress may exhibit lower compliance rates.

Different departments within hospitals face unique challenges when it comes to hand hygiene compliance. For instance, Pittet (2001) found that compliance rates are particularly low in departments with high patient turnover, such as emergency and radiology. In these settings, healthcare workers are often under significant time pressure, making it difficult to consistently follow hand hygiene protocols. Similarly, the physical environment of certain departments, including the availability of hand hygiene stations, can impact compliance rates (Erasmus et al., 2009).

Various strategies have been implemented to improve hand hygiene compliance, with mixed results. Educational programs and awareness campaigns are among the most commonly used interventions (WHO, 2009). These programs aim to increase healthcare workers' knowledge about the importance of hand hygiene and the proper techniques for handwashing. However, education alone is often insufficient to sustain long-term compliance. Performance feedback and reminders have also been employed as additional strategies to reinforce hand hygiene practices (Allegranzi&Pittet, 2009). These interventions can be effective, but their impact can vary based on the specific context of the department in which they are implemented.

A study by Erasmus et al. (2009) explored the reasons for poor hand hygiene compliance among healthcare workers and found that a lack of positive role models and insufficient evidence of the effectiveness of hand hygiene were major barriers. This suggests that fostering a culture of accountability and ensuring that healthcare workers witness the benefits of hand hygiene in preventing infections could be key to improving compliance rates. Additionally, the role of leadership and management support has been identified as a crucial factor in promoting adherence to hand hygiene guidelines (Allegranzi&Pittet, 2009).

Despite the challenges, some interventions have shown promise in improving compliance. Multimodal strategies that combine education, performance feedback, reminders, and institutional support are considered the most effective approach for enhancing hand hygiene practices (WHO, 2009). These strategies address multiple barriers simultaneously, making them more likely to succeed in diverse healthcare environments. For example, providing adequate access to hand hygiene stations, fostering a supportive work environment, and integrating hand hygiene into daily routines can all contribute to sustained compliance.

This literature review highlights the complexity of hand hygiene compliance in healthcare settings. While various strategies have been developed to improve adherence, their effectiveness often depends on the specific departmental context and the presence of supportive leadership. By evaluating the effectiveness of hand hygiene compliance strategies across different departments in a tertiary hospital, this study aims to provide insights that can inform the development of targeted interventions to improve compliance and reduce the risk of HAIs.

Methodology

This study was conducted in a tertiary hospital to evaluate the effectiveness of hand hygiene compliance strategies across different departments. A mixed-methods approach was utilized, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to gain a comprehensive understanding of hand hygiene practices within the hospital.

Data Collection

The study involved data collection from three main departments: emergency, radiology, and intensive care. Compliance rates were assessed through direct observation of healthcare workers, using a standardized hand hygiene observation tool adapted from the World Health Organization (WHO, 2009) guidelines. Observations were conducted over a period of six months, with trained observers positioned discreetly to minimize the Hawthorne effect. Observers recorded instances of hand hygiene opportunities and actual compliance among healthcare workers, including nurses, doctors, and support staff.

In addition to direct observation, structured interviews were conducted with healthcare workers from each department to identify barriers and facilitators to hand hygiene compliance. Interviews focused on factors such as workload, departmental culture, access to hand hygiene resources, and perceived importance of hand hygiene. A total of 30 healthcare workers participated in the interviews, including nurses, physicians, and ancillary staff.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the observational study were analyzed using descriptive statistics to calculate compliance rates across the three departments. Differences in compliance rates were compared using chi-square tests to determine if there were statistically significant variations between departments. Compliance rates were also analyzed based on the type of healthcare worker to identify any role-specific trends.

Qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. Transcripts were coded to identify common themes related to barriers and facilitators of hand hygiene compliance. Thematic analysis helped to uncover patterns and contextual factors that influenced compliance in each department, providing valuable insights into how departmental culture and environment affected hand hygiene practices.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the ethics committee. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all healthcare workers involved in the interviews. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the study, and all data were de-identified before analysis.

Findings

Quantitative Findings

The quantitative analysis of hand hygiene compliance rates across the three departments revealed significant variations. Table 1 presents the compliance rates observed in each department. The intensive care unit (ICU) demonstrated the highest compliance rate at 78%, followed by the emergency department (ED) at 65%, and the radiology department with the lowest rate at 52%. Chi-square analysis indicated that these differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Department	Observed Opportunities	Compliance Rate (%)
Intensive Care	350	78
Emergency	300	65
Radiology	250	52

Further analysis by healthcare worker role showed that nurses had the highest compliance rate at 72%, followed by physicians at 63%, and ancillary staff at 55% (Table 2). Differences in compliance rates between roles were also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Healthcare Worker Role	Observed Opportunities	Compliance Rate (%)
Nurses	400	72
Physicians	300	63
Ancillary Staff	200	55

Qualitative Findings

The qualitative data from the structured interviews were analyzed to identify themes and sub-themes related to barriers and facilitators of hand hygiene compliance. Three main themes emerged: workload and time constraints, departmental culture and leadership, and resource availability.

Theme 1: Workload and Time Constraints

- Sub-theme 1.1: High Patient Turnover: Healthcare workers, particularly in the emergency department, reported that high patient turnover made it challenging to adhere to hand hygiene protocols. One participant stated, "The constant flow of patients means there's little time to think about hand hygiene between cases."
- Sub-theme 1.2: Staffing Shortages: Staffing shortages were frequently cited as a barrier. A nurse from the ICU mentioned, "We are often understaffed, which makes it difficult to maintain proper hand hygiene when we are focused on providing care."

Theme 2: Departmental Culture and Leadership

- Sub-theme 2.1: Leadership Support: Participants highlighted the importance of leadership in promoting hand hygiene. A physician noted, "In departments where the leadership actively supports hand hygiene practices, compliance is noticeably better."
- Sub-theme 2.2: Role Models: The presence of positive role models was also emphasized. An ancillary staff member from radiology said, "Seeing senior staff consistently follow hand hygiene practices encourages me to do the same."

Theme 3: Resource Availability

- Sub-theme 3.1: Access to Hand Hygiene Stations: Limited access to hand hygiene stations was identified

as a barrier, particularly in the radiology department. One participant stated, "Sometimes the hand sanitizers are not conveniently located, which discourages frequent use."

- Sub-theme 3.2: Availability of Supplies: The availability of hand hygiene supplies, such as soap and alcohol-based hand rubs, was seen as a facilitator. A nurse remarked, "When supplies are readily available, it's much easier to comply with hand hygiene guidelines."

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings provided a holistic understanding of the factors influencing hand hygiene compliance across different departments. The quantitative data highlighted significant variations in compliance rates, while the qualitative data provided context to these differences, identifying specific barriers and facilitators that could be addressed to improve overall compliance.

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the variability in hand hygiene compliance across different departments and healthcare worker roles within a tertiary hospital. The results indicate that compliance rates are highest in the ICU and lowest in the radiology department, with significant differences between healthcare worker roles. These differences underscore the need for tailored interventions that address the specific challenges faced by each department and healthcare worker category.

The high compliance rate observed in the ICU can be attributed to the critical nature of patient care in this setting, where the consequences of HAIs are particularly severe. ICU staff may also benefit from a higher level of awareness regarding the importance of hand hygiene, which is often emphasized through ongoing training and education. Conversely, the lower compliance rates in the radiology department suggest that the less acute nature of care, combined with limited access to hand hygiene stations, may contribute to reduced adherence to hand hygiene practices. This finding is consistent with previous research that has shown that physical barriers and workload can impact compliance (Pittet, 2001; Erasmus et al., 2009).

The thematic analysis of the qualitative data provided important insights into the barriers and facilitators of hand hygiene compliance. Workload and time constraints were consistently cited as significant barriers, particularly in high-pressure environments like the emergency department. Healthcare workers reported feeling overwhelmed by the volume of patients, which limited their ability to prioritize hand hygiene. This finding emphasizes the need for staffing adjustments or workflow improvements that can reduce the burden on healthcare workers, enabling them to adhere to hand hygiene guidelines more consistently.

The influence of departmental culture and leadership on hand hygiene compliance was another key theme identified in this study. Departments with strong leadership support and positive role models demonstrated higher compliance rates. This finding is in line with previous studies that have highlighted the role of leadership in fostering a culture of safety and promoting adherence to infection control practices (Allegranzi&Pittet, 2009). Efforts to improve hand hygiene compliance should therefore include initiatives that enhance leadership engagement and promote positive role modeling by senior staff members.

Resource availability, including access to hand hygiene stations and supplies, was also identified as a critical factor influencing compliance. Limited access to hand hygiene stations was particularly problematic in the radiology department, suggesting that infrastructural improvements, such as increasing the number of conveniently located hand hygiene stations, could significantly enhance compliance rates. Ensuring a consistent supply of hand hygiene products is also essential, as healthcare workers are more likely to adhere to hand hygiene practices when supplies are readily available (WHO, 2009).

The quantitative and qualitative findings of this study support the use of multimodal strategies to improve hand hygiene compliance. Education alone is insufficient to sustain long-term improvements, and a combination of interventions, including performance feedback, leadership support, and infrastructural enhancements, is necessary to achieve sustained compliance. The WHO's multimodal hand hygiene improvement strategy, which includes system change, training, evaluation, and reminders, remains a relevant and effective approach for addressing the challenges identified in this study (WHO, 2009).

This study has several implications for practice. First, hospital administrators should consider department-specific factors when designing hand hygiene interventions. Departments such as radiology, which face unique challenges related to physical infrastructure and workload, may require targeted solutions that differ from those implemented in high-compliance areas like the ICU. Second, leadership engagement should be prioritized, with efforts to encourage senior staff to act as role models for hand hygiene compliance. Finally, ensuring adequate staffing and improving access to hand hygiene resources are critical steps toward enhancing compliance rates across all departments.

In conclusion, improving hand hygiene compliance in tertiary hospitals requires a comprehensive and context-specific approach. By addressing the unique challenges faced by different departments and healthcare worker roles, hospitals can develop targeted interventions that enhance compliance and ultimately reduce the risk of healthcare-associated infections. Future research should focus on evaluating the long-term effectiveness of tailored interventions and exploring innovative solutions, such as technology-based reminders, to further improve hand hygiene practices.

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